

Paedophile Hunters:

A Critical Review of Practice.

Thomas Leggett

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15862937 | ISSN: 2977-1676

The Journal of
Crime & Justice
Dissertations

About: The Journal of Crime & Justice Dissertations (JCJD) is an online platform for student dissertations. The JCJD is a London Metropolitan University [Crime Lab project](#) which was established in 2023.

The JCJD does not make use of a peer-review process as is typical with standard academic journals. Rather the JCJD serves as a platform for showcasing high-achieving student dissertations that relate to the concepts of social justice and social harm. All dissertations are sourced from reputable universities and all dissertations have received a 1st class grade. The JCJD makes use of an inspection process but this is only to ensure that the minimum requirements of the platform are upheld (it is not a peer-review process). JCJD publications should be read in this context, the publications are students' work and should not be used in the same manner as rigorously peer-reviewed content. For a full disclaimer regarding the JCJD and for more details regarding the inspection process for dissertations, please visit the website journalcjd.org.

Director (Editor in Chief): Shaun S. Yates.

Executive Committee: Ellada Larionidou, James Alexander, Jade Benn, Gordana Uzelac, Emek Yuce Zeyrek-Rios, Eden Zaidner, Denise Morrison, Xingwei Li, Isifu Mwase, Kevin J. Brazant, Elna Konstantinidou, Karen Dyer, Elaine Isadora Thomas, Ronke Shoderu, Finley MacDonald, Katrina Ozcakir Mozova, Corinne Funnell, Wendy Akpareva and Anthony Schembri.

Address: London Metropolitan University, 166-220 Holloway Road, London, N7 8DB.

www.journalcjd.org

British Library Registered ISSN: 2977-1676

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15862937>

© 2025 by The Journal of Crime & Justice Dissertations (JCJD).

The Journal of
Crime & Justice
Dissertations

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank the following people who have helped me undertake this research and achieve my degree:

Firstly, I would like to thank my dissertation supervisor, Dave Thompson, for his continued support, critique and advice.

Secondly, my mum Karen, for being a constant source of support and for proof-reading my work – often challenging my phrasing and formatting.

Thirdly, thank you to my girlfriend Mya, for putting up with my stress and listening to my long political rants despite having minimal interest. Your care and support have helped me get through these three years.

And finally, this project is dedicated to my daughter Evelyn, this degree has been a step further to providing the future you deserve. You are my ultimate motivation and top priority; I love you eternally.

Abstract

This dissertation examined the methods paedophile hunters employ during their investigations and sting operations, with particular note to the contentious aspects of their practice and how these practices can delegitimise their work. This project utilises an integrative literature review methodology to apply empirically tested theoretical knowledge to this contemporary topic in order to contribute to the base of knowledge. The main themes identified in this project were: online public shaming, disintegrative shaming, inconsistent investigations, and poor accountability and transparency. This project proposes a harm reduction approach to paedophile hunting in which the aim is to legitimise paedophile hunter groups through concentrating on intelligence collection and ceasing practices which can cause harm. This proposition highlights the inadequate elements of paedophile hunter practice and seeks to ameliorate these aspects of practice in order to reduce harm to the targets of their investigations and their families, the criminal justice system, and the paedophile hunter groups themselves.

Contents Page

Acknowledgements	1
Abstract	2
Contents Page	3
Chapter 1: Introduction	5
1.1 Background Research / Rationale.....	5
1.2 Aims and Objectives	6
1.3 Research Questions.....	6
1.4 Methodology	6
1.4.1 Search Criteria	7
1.4.2 Ethical Considerations	7
1.4.3 Structure of Dissertation	8
Chapter 2: Literature Review	9
2.1 Defining Paedophile Hunters.....	9
2.2 The Process of ‘Hunting’	9
2.3 Responses from the Criminal Justice System	11
2.4 ECHR Article 6 and 8.....	12
2.5 Public Responses to Paedophile Hunters	13
2.6 Legitimacy	14
2.7 Controversies in Paedophile Hunter Practice.....	15
Chapter 3: Unregulated Retribution	18
3.1 Introduction.....	18
3.2 Disintegrative Shaming.....	18
3.2.1 Online Public Shaming	18
3.2.2 Labels and Insults	19
3.2.3 The Impacts of Disintegrative Shaming	20
3.2.4 Inconsistent Investigatory Practices	20
3.2.5 Undermining the Criminal Justice System	21
3.2.6 Doxing.....	21
3.2.7 The Side Effect of Recorded Confrontations	22

3.3 The Flawed Rationales of Recorded Confrontations	23
3.3.1 Public Protection	23
3.3.2 ‘We’re recording for your own protection and ours’	23
3.3.3 Recording for the Purposes of Gaining a Confession.....	24
3.5 Conclusion and Effects on Legitimacy	24
Chapter 4: A Harm Reduction Approach To Paedophile Hunting	26
4.1 Introduction.....	26
4.2 Improving the Quality of Evidence	26
4.3 Recording Confrontations	27
4.4 Doxing.....	28
4.5 Publishing Post-Trial Reports.....	29
4.6 Transparency and Accountability	30
4.7 Harm Reduction	30
4.8 Protecting Due Process	31
4.9 Conclusion	31
Chapter 5: Conclusion.....	33
Case Reference List.....	35
Reference List.....	36

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Background Research / Rationale

Since the 1970s the threat of paedophilia and 'stranger danger' has been engrained in the collective consciousness (Adler, 2001) through the media amplification of news stories detailing accounts of children being sexually abused or murdered by unknown adults (Marsh and Melville, 2011; McDonald, 2014); despite the fact that more frequently the adult is known to the victim (Wodda, 2018; Jewkes and Wykes, 2012). The moral panic surrounding paedophiles created by the media consequently caused a culture of fear among parents (Furedi, 2002) in which moral outrage and vigilantism is an unsurprising result (Critcher, 2009). This media-generated outrage can be exemplified by the News of the World's 'naming and shaming' campaign in 2000, in which the newspaper notified the public of the age, appearance, and location of paedophiles across Britain in order to stoke public tensions (Bell, 2003; Critcher 2002). This resulted in groups of vigilantes protesting and rioting outside the homes of 'known' paedophiles, causing the families living there being forced to flee to safety (Marsh and Melville, 2011; Evans, 2003). Two men later committed suicide as a result of the unwanted publicity and vigilantism caused by this campaign (Silke, 2001). The media-induced moral panic of 1990s and 2000s surrounding 'stranger danger' had developed alongside the advent of the internet and introduced the concept of 'cyber-paeds' (Jewkes and Wykes, 2012) and online grooming.

During the 1990s the internet had become widely adopted and increasingly afforded people access to computers in the privacy of their own homes (Jewkes and Yar, 2010), a consequence of this was the increased capability for online criminal behaviour such as Child Sexual Exploitation (CSE) (Ost, 2009). The expansion of internet usage created a complex issue for policing (Harkin and Whelan, 2021) in which there is a gap of technical knowledge to investigate and police online crimes such as grooming and CSE (Noble, 2017; Wolf and Pruitt, 2019). The police were, and still are, relatively technologically inept at investigating CSE as the methods of investigation are far detached from traditional policing (Johnson et al., 2020); this often means that the task of investigating online CSE is delegated to a very limited number of specialist digital forensic analysts within the police (Hadlington et al., 2018; Holt et al., 2015). Within this context, Silke (2001) posits that vigilantism arises in a perceived vacuum of policing where the police are seen to willingness or capacity to investigate (Chang et al., 2018; Walton and Penfold, 2023). This in turn invites the pluralisation of policing to involve non-state actors (Hussey et al., 2022) such as paedophile hunter groups (PHGs). Paedophile hunters are arguably no different from the anti-paedophile protestors of the 2000s, they simply have more technological tools at their

disposal (Tippett, 2022) and due to the online publicity (both positive and negative) afforded by the news and social media, the number of active PHGs has continued to increase (De Rond et al., 2021).

NPCC reported in 2021 that there is a realistic probability that community tensions will be sustained against those perceived as negatively impacting on the safety of vulnerable community members (2021), this highlights the notion that paedophile hunter activities will not cease without criminalisation of non-state policing or, alternatively, an active collaboration between the police and paedophile hunters. It is unlikely that citizen-led policing initiatives will end without criminalisation, and so it is of significant importance to investigate the issues in paedophile hunter practice in order to reduce public harm.

1.2 Aims and Objectives

The process in which paedophile hunters conduct their investigations is the main point of contention among the police, media, public, and academics. This study aims to analyse the illegitimate aspects of their processes of investigation and propose an ethically and legally robust practice framework to increase the likelihood of successful convictions of those charged with the offence of attempting to meet a child for sex.

1. To identify and critically analyse contentious aspects of paedophile hunter practice.
2. To evaluate the effects of these practices on the legitimacy of paedophile hunters as a heterogeneous group.
3. To recommend alternative practices for paedophile hunters that addresses the illegitimising effects of current practices and promotes harm reduction.

1.3 Research Questions

1. What processes and strategies do paedophile hunters currently employ and why are some of them considered problematic by the public and criminal justice system?
2. How can paedophile hunter practice be adapted to improve the legitimacy of paedophile hunting and reduce the potential of harm to the public?

1.4 Methodology

This project will utilise an integrative literature review (ILR) in order to evaluate the scope of the current literature and establish new lines of enquiry and contribute conceptually to the literature (Snyder, 2019). An ILR differs from a systematic review in that an ILR allows the use of broader sources, such as discussion papers and government documents, which can provide valuable insights rather than focussing exclusively on secondary data (Lubbe et al., 2020). An ILR will be beneficial to this project

because the search of literature will focus on specific themes relevant to the project to synthesise and integrate new theoretical knowledge rather than a comprehensive review of the literature that is merely descriptive (Torraco, 2005; Randolph, 2009), and considerably more time consuming (Thomas et al., 2015).

An ILR is the most appropriate method for researching paedophile hunter practices because of the maturity of the literature (Torraco, 2005); paedophile hunting is a contemporary topic and as such there is limited research in this area, so in order to generate new theoretical knowledge it is important to be able to apply more widely developed theories to a contemporary topic. Literature based research is epistemologically utilitarian in that it seeks to maximise benefit to the base of knowledge and minimise harm to participants (Suri, 2020); this epistemological position has influenced the decision to limit the ethical implications that this research would face while collecting empirical data. This epistemological position has influenced the aims of this project, primarily the aim to reduce the amount of harm caused by paedophile hunter investigations.

1.4.1 Search Criteria

In order to limit reporting bias influencing the outcome of this research (Drucker et al., 2016), the search strategy implemented in this research will specify an inclusion criteria prior to surveying the literature for sources to review. The inclusion criteria for this research consist of peer-reviewed research articles, books or other texts pertaining to a variety of search terms, including: Paedophile hunter; Doxing; Entrapment; Vigilantism; Digilantism; Grooming; Disintegrative shaming; Legitimacy; Stigma.

1.4.2 Ethical Considerations

The ethical concerns surrounding this project are predominantly potential harms to the researcher (Sieber, 1993) due to the sensitive subject of the project, which can be minimised through literature-based research. The potential for harm to participants is significantly lower in this project compared to other empirical studies due to lack of reliance on participant data. In order to limit the risk of 'emotional burnout' (Butler et al., 2017), a mental wellbeing plan will be employed which includes taking breaks from research and seeking support from personal contacts and contacts within the university such as the university's student wellbeing team.

1.4.3 Structure of Dissertation

This dissertation consists of a broad literature review on the topic of paedophile hunters and the various implications of their actions. This is followed by a chapter discussing the contentious aspects of paedophile hunting and the effects that their methods of investigation have on the legitimacy of PHGs. Subsequently this research will propose alternative practices to ameliorate the harmful effects of current paedophile hunter practice.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Defining Paedophile Hunters

'Paedophile hunter' is the colloquial name for cyber-vigilantes who investigate the online grooming of children and seek punishment for those found to be grooming (Walton and Penfold, 2023). Though the name 'paedophile hunter' has been critiqued as being problematic (Ireland, 2022) for its witch-hunt imagery, it is the most cited name for this phenomenon and as such this project will adopt this term. Purshouse (2020, p.388) positions paedophile hunting as a "form of grassroots pluralized policing endeavour, with a key difference being that it blends online interactions with real-world confrontations" however this phenomenon could be better understood as a form of 'digilantism' (Stratton, Powell and Cameron, 2017), where online activists seek retribution in the offline world (Sorell, 2019).

Hussey et al. (2022) propose different rationales for paedophile hunters to conduct investigations, one motivation for hunting is to protect children, constructing themselves as saviours and their suspects as evil predators (Chiang et al., 2023; De Rond et al., 2021). Another motivation is that they perceive that the police are inept at investigating online CSE and that a PHG can catch predators in absence of a competent police force (Gillespie, 2019). The child-protectionism rationale (Yardley et al., 2016) for paedophile hunting is obfuscated by paedophile hunters being perceived as undermining the police, this will be discussed in the following chapter.

2.2 The Process of 'Hunting'

Paedophile hunters utilise a variety of techniques in their investigations, as a heterogeneous group the methods of each PHG vary considerably. Some paedophile hunters employ tactics which mimic the police, but they are unbound by the legal framework that the police are (Hadjimatheou, 2019), this distinction is the cause of legal and social controversy around the activity of paedophile hunting because they are extralegally performing the duties of the police which has serious moral and political implications (Purshouse, 2020). There is a philosophical divide within the PHG community – those who operate altruistically to gather evidence and secure prosecutions, and those who operate to shame their targets on social media. The typology of paedophile hunters has yet to be researched, however acknowledging the differences between PHGs highlights the different justifications and motivations for 'hunting'. Paedophile hunters operate at varying levels of professionalism (Hadjimatheou, 2019) but

typically follow a similar design for their investigation process, the heterogeneity of paedophile hunters is significant to note because the methods of investigation are where controversies lie.

Paedophile hunters typically employ a linear five-stage investigation model, which includes: Creating a decoy profile, Using the decoy to attract targets, Collecting 'evidence' in the form of chatlogs, Performing a recorded sting operation, Reporting to the police. This section will outline these methods further and how these methods may vary within PHGs.

The initial stage of the process involves hunters creating a pseudo-online-dating-profile, called a 'decoy', which pretends to be a child below the age of consent (Walton and Penfold, 2023). There are differences between PHGs in that some choose to use images of real children for the profile, and others use photos of adults (Purshouse, 2020). Using photos of children has definite ethical implications, yet using photos of adults also has ethical problems because the adults could be ordinary innocent people having their photo used for this purpose, it is also questionable because the 'suspect' may believe the profile is that of an adult at face value.

This decoy profile is then used to engage in conversations with other users of the site, there is additional variability in PHGs that make the initial contact with others on these sites or if they strictly reply to messages rather than seek out to 'entrap' individuals. The decoy will continue to text the suspect until the suspect explicitly states their intentions, this is done to prove to the police that the individual intends to meet the decoy with the intent of sexually abusing a child. The evidentiary standard is decided by the PHG without adherence to PACE codes which often means that the evidence collected is insufficient to prosecute the suspect in court (Purshouse, 2020). The paedophile hunters then print out the 'chatlogs' (the chain of texts between the decoy and the suspect) and arrange to meet with the suspect. This concludes the digital portion of the investigation process.

The paedophile hunters then conduct a 'sting' operation wherein they confront the suspect (Frampton, 2022). The sting operation is sometimes conducted in busy public places such as parks or town centres or sometimes at the suspect's home (Sorell, 2019). The treatment of the suspect also varies among paedophile hunters. Some groups are empathetic to the suspect's mental health or disability needs whereas other groups can be seen to shout at, insult, threaten, or attack the suspect (Sorell, 2019; Favarel-Garrigues, 2019; Ireland, 2022). Video recording and live streaming are a prevalent feature of the sting operation (Tippett, 2022), recorded confrontations ensure higher visibility of the sting operation and thus increase the shame experienced by the individual (De Rond et al., 2021); other

justifications for recorded confrontations will be discussed in the next chapter. Posting footage of the confrontation online often serves to accelerate deleterious consequences for the suspect and their family (Purshouse, 2020), this is a form of severe stigmatisation via social media (Hussey et al., 2022). Recorded confrontations is a contentious feature of paedophile hunting (Campbell, 2016) because these videos are often published as entertainment for those seeking moral outrage (Trottier, 2017).

The paedophile hunters will then detain the suspect while they call the police. The police then attend the site of the sting operation, and the chat-logs are handed over to the police officer to examine, and if the evidence is compelling on a surface-level then the suspect is arrested (Sorell, 2019). The paedophile hunters will typically post the recorded confrontation on social media, often attached with personal information of the suspect (doxing) to further shame the suspect (Loveluck, 2019; Trottier, 2017). The posting of the confrontation on social media typically happens on the same day as the sting operation, which can undermine the judicial process (Chiang et al., 2023), however some more 'professionalised' groups opt not to post the confrontation until after the suspect has stood trial in court in order to ensure a fair trial.

2.3 Responses from the Criminal Justice System

The criminal justice system has a complex and contradicting relationship with paedophile hunters (Frampton, 2022). The official stance of the police and CPS is absolute discouragement of the activities of paedophile hunters (CPS, 2020); yet police forces across the country still conduct arrests and accept evidence obtained by paedophile hunters and the courts still use the evidence at trial (Gillespie, 2019). While the police as an organisation discourage paedophile hunters (NPCC, 2017; Gillespie, 2019), each force has its own guidance on how to appropriately manage these groups (Walton and Penfold, 2023); some forces have suggested potentially collaborating with paedophile hunters (Police Professional, 2017). In 2017 Jim Gamble, former head of CEOP, proposed that the police should recruit paedophile hunters as special constables in order to legitimise the work they do (Gillespie, 2019). Since Gamble's comment it seems the police have remained firm in their disapproval of paedophile hunting, this could be to prevent PHGs from undermining the police. Purshouse (2020) notes that openness to working with paedophile hunters serves to encourage other non-state actors to conduct unregulated investigations, which essentially circumvents the rule of law.

The CPS perceives paedophile hunters' investigatory procedures to be illegitimate and refers to them as 'vigilantes' in their legal guidance (CPS, 2020). Despite this overt disapproval, the number of successful prosecutions using evidence obtained by paedophile hunters has increased over the last

decade; according to a BBC News (2019) Freedom Of Information request “The number of cases involving paedophile hunter evidence had more than tripled in the space of two years - rising from 57 in 2016 to 179 in 2018”. The CPS’s reliance on paedophile hunter evidence while simultaneously condemning their actions illustrates the complexity of the relationship between PHGs and the CPS.

2.4 ECHR Article 6 and 8

The European Convention of Human Rights (ECHR) has previously been used to defend PHG targets, in particular it has been argued that paedophile hunter evidence violates Article 6, the right to a fair trial, and Article 8, the right to a private life. Both these defences, respectively, have been dismissed in benchmark cases (Walton and Penfold, 2023; Purshouse, 2020; McPherson, 2020; Stark, 2018). *Sutherland (Appellant) v Her Majesty’s Advocate (Respondent) (Scotland) [2020] UKSC 32*, the Supreme Court found no breach of Article 8 on the grounds that the individuals’ right to a private life was secondary to the child’s rights, albeit there was no ‘real’ child in danger (Walton and Penfold, 2023). This decision from the Court has set a precedent for the use of paedophile hunter evidence in future trials. Holmes (2021) notes that the Court’s decision enables private organisations to potentially interfere with an individual’s right to a private life in a way that the police are unable to do due to legal safeguards, creating a “two-tiered system of liability for interferences” (p.220). This is significant because the complexity of the relationship between PHGs and the criminal justice system has resulted in discouragement of their methods but approval of their results.

The contradictive stance regarding paedophile hunter evidence is not unique to CPS, but rather the police as well. A cynical interpretation of this dynamic could be that police discouragement of PHG activities is a prerequisite for the evidence obtained by paedophile hunters to be used in court; creating a legislative scenario similar to the ‘silver platter doctrine’¹ in the United States (Gray et al., 2012). In order for PHG evidence to be used to convict somebody, the police must explicitly discourage their behaviour. This discouragement allows the police to circumvent Covert Human Information Source (CHIS) rules which would make paedophile hunters liable to abide by the Regulation of Investigatory Powers Act 2000 (RIPA), and thus the paedophile hunters’ methods of obtaining evidence would be inadmissible in court (CPS, 2022). If a paedophile hunter was adopted as a CHIS, then a defence of entrapment could be applicable in court because the paedophile hunter would be classed as a state actor; which is otherwise unapplicable to private individuals and non-state actors such as paedophile

¹ The ‘silver platter doctrine’ was a United States legal principle that allowed evidence that has been illegally obtained by a non-state actor (through torture, coercion, or other means) to be legally accepted so long as the state actor did not request, encourage, or participate in the collection of the evidence.

hunters (Stark, 2018). Gillespie (2019) comments that a failure to authorise PHGs as a CHIS does not make their methods unlawful and thus they could not violate Article 6 of the ECHR because they are non-state actors, and the entrapment argument cannot apply. This was evidenced during the *R v Walters* [T20167262] and *R v Ali* cases [T20160897] in which it was determined that although PHGs fall within the definition of a CHIS, they are ineligible to become a CHIS until the point at which they hand their evidence to the police, and at that point the investigation portion of their sting has concluded and so the RIPA rules could not retroactively apply. This means that paedophile hunters are able to submit evidence to the police 'on a silver platter' and avert scrutiny into the methods they used to obtain the evidence.

The various court rulings discussed above highlight the way in which non-state actors could conceivably bypass legal investigatory safeguards; however this is merely speculative.

2.5 Public Responses to Paedophile Hunters

The culture of fear surrounding sex offending has been cultivated by the media throughout the past 50 years and has inextricably impacted the public's negative view on anybody accused of sex offences (Furedi, 2002; Harper et al., 2024). Society almost unanimously feels anger and disgust towards individuals who exhibit paraphilic interests (Janke, 2018). The communal hatred towards sex offenders coupled with declining confidence in police efficacy (Hamilton and Black, 2022; Campbell, 2016) seemingly generates a population sympathetic to the cause of paedophile hunting (Chang and Poon, 2016; Silke, 2001). Arguably the most vocal advocates of paedophile hunters can be found on social media sites such as Facebook where users like, share, and comment on videos of sting operations posted by paedophile hunters (Dunsby and Howes, 2018). The public appetite for this disintegrative shaming can be a legitimising force in which the paedophile hunters can present themselves as providing a public service (Ireland, 2022). It is important to note that the comments on paedophile hunter's social media pages are an unreliable linguistic metric of support, these pages quickly become an echo-chamber in which similar opinions are shared and repeated while contrarian opinions are met with rejection and hostility (Bruns, 2017; Tippett, 2022). The echo-chamber of PHG social media pages prevent the PHG's audience from contemplating the negative aspects and consequences of paedophile hunting, this will be elaborated in the next chapter.

Attitudes towards sex offenders have been empirically explored in stigmatisation discourse (Harper et al., 2017; Lehmann et al., 2020; Olver and Barlow, 2010), however there is little empirical research about public attitudes towards paedophile hunters. Frampton's (2021) unprecedented research on the

public perceptions of paedophile hunters found conflicting views. The majority of respondents believed that paedophile hunter's evidence should be admissible in court, yet half the respondents felt that paedophile hunters did not provide a worthwhile service. The public ambivalence towards paedophile hunters and their methods of investigation could potentially be the result of over-saturated media stories about paedophiles in addition to the echo-chamber social media pages of PHGs. The public's uncertain stance on paedophile hunting is analogous to the criminal justice systems' contradicting stances of paedophile hunters and the evidence they collect.

2.6 Legitimacy

Paedophile hunters could conceivably depend on the support of the public to justify their existence in absence of support from the state, the organisational legitimacy of paedophile hunters depends on approval from multiple benefactors including: the public, the police and CPS (as an extension of the state). When legitimacy is conceptualised as a property or resource, it can fluctuate depending on sociopolitical situations (Suddaby et al., 2017), in this context media coverage of successful convictions using paedophile hunter evidence could legitimise the existence of PHGs. Legitimacy can also be viewed as a perception from the community, Weber (1968) proposed that an organisation's legitimacy is dependent on three metrics: longevity, trustworthiness, and if the organisation follows logical or legal procedures. Noppe et al. (2017) supplements Weber's definition although they distinguish between normative and empirical legitimacy; normative legitimacy is based on an objective criteria similar to Weber's definition, however empirical legitimacy is dependent on the perception of civilians. The concept of empirical legitimacy is fundamentally supported by Suddaby et al. (2017) in their definition of legitimacy as a 'sociocognitive perception or evaluation' in which legitimacy is gained through the perception of others. This is significant because many PHGs rely on social media engagement to motivate them and justify the existence of their group, thus legitimising themselves through the views of their audience. Much of the literature surrounding legitimacy seems underpinned by social constructionism, in that something is not deemed legitimate until the label of legitimacy has been ascribed to it.

An organisation that faces stigmatic labels, such as paedophile hunters being labelled vigilantes, can be viewed as simultaneously legitimate and illegitimate (Hudson and Okhuysen, 2009) through assessment of the core practices of the organisation. The organisational stigmatisation facing paedophile hunters derives from the assumed homogeneity of paedophile hunter organisations, often neglecting the variations of legitimacy in different organisations (this will be discussed in chapter three). Some PHGs may wish to gain or improve their legitimacy in the eyes of the public to gain passive support and/or

the police to gain active support (Suchman, 1995); yet it is important to note that some organisations may not wish to gain legitimacy at all but would rather conduct their practices laterally to the criminal justice system. Some PHGs are antipathetic towards the police for their perceived failure to police or investigate CSE, accordingly they may wish to conduct investigations completely independent of the police as they are disdainful towards them.

Some paedophile hunters strive to garner legitimacy through imitation of normative organisations such as the police; by adopting the characteristics of the police as a legitimate authoritative power the public's perception of the hunter's legitimacy may increase (Suddaby et al., 2017; Johnson et al., 2006). The police as an institution have been increasingly scrutinised in the past few decades for instances of police brutality (Deflem, 2016), high-profile murder cases involving police officers (Cunningham, 2023), and the subsequent social movements that stemmed from these cases of police malpractice. The Casey review (Casey, 2023) further damaged the police's 'protector' status by concluding that the police are institutionally racist, misogynistic and homophobic. These instances of scrutiny into police behaviour often leads to mistrust of the police, and if the police cannot be trusted by their public then their legitimacy as an institution declines (Sharp et al., 2008; Morrell et al., 2019; Tippett, 2022). Seemingly there is an opportunity for non-state policing initiatives to become legitimised at the expense of delegitimisation of the police, this is a possible explanation for the rising number of PHGs (De Rond et al., 2021).

2.7 Controversies in Paedophile Hunter Practice

There are many problematic practices that feature in paedophile hunting, including: live streaming, doxing, inconsistent investigatory practices, lack of transparency and accountability, and the threat of undermining the criminal justice system and due process (Purshouse, 2020).

Perhaps the most problematic features of paedophile hunting are recorded confrontations, doxing, and the subsequent posting of the confrontation online. The motive for these retributive tactics is public humiliation that is proliferated by an enduring online record of the confrontation (Purshouse, 2020; De Rond et al., 2021). The permanent record of the confrontation serves to exacerbate the stigmatising effect on the suspect and doxing incites others to blackmail, harass, and verbally or physically assault the suspect (Trottier, 2020; Sorell, 2019; Noble, 2017; Ireland, 2023). The stigma of being accused of a sexual offence can often overshadow whether the suspect is found guilty or not, the accusation alone can ruin their reputation regardless of a conviction (Harper et al., 2024). There are many cases of the suspect self-harming and committing suicide as the result of recorded confrontations (Hussey et al.,

2022; Purshouse, 2020; Trottier, 2017; Tippett, 2022). This is particularly problematic as recorded confrontations are often posted online before the suspect has been tried in court, which bypasses the due process system and thus the suspect is presumed to be guilty and the stigmatisation of this can often lead to their suicide (Cohen et al., 2019). An unfair collateral effect of doxing is that the families of accused paedophiles experience secondary stigmatisation (Evans et al., 2021) and humiliation (Hadjimatheou, 2019). There are cases where doxing the suspected paedophiles' home address has resulted in their house being burned down (Allison, 2000), displacing the innocent family of the suspected paedophile. This begs the question: is it the paedophile hunter's objective to provide evidence to the police and CPS? Or is their objective to humiliate and shame their target as a form of retributive social justice? These questions may recur throughout this research paper, however, irrespective of the internal motivations of PHGs, the way in which they are able to undermine the investigatory role of the police will continue to be a critical issue within the criminal justice discourse.

While many PHGs adopt similar investigation designs involving decoys, chatlogs, stings and confrontations, there is variation in the investigation techniques used between different groups (Campbell, 2016). Since paedophile hunters are not bound by the same investigatory framework as the police, the standard of evidence that they consider to be sufficient for prosecution may not meet the same evidentiary requirements that a police investigation would have thus the suspect may be released without charge. There are occasions where paedophile hunters wrongly accuse people (Noble, 2017), use disproportionate force during confrontations (Sorrell, 2019; Ireland, 2023) and face charges for false imprisonment or assault (Purshouse, 2020). Paedophile hunters may not wish to act under a code of conduct because having a working relationship with the police would require them to abide by RIPA and would be unable to conduct covert investigations. Paedophile hunters may not be bound by the same investigatory frameworks as the police, but an informal code of conduct might professionalise PHGs and mitigate concerns around their practice, this will be the subject of chapter four.

Weber's (1968) conception of legitimacy states that an organisation must be trustworthy in order to be legitimate; yet currently there is a lack of organisational accountability and transparency in the work of paedophile hunting (Frampton, 2022; Ireland, 2023). The police are held accountable by RIPA and PACE codes of practice when investigating criminal offences, this accountability preserves the legitimacy of the police as an organisation. There is an increasing reliance on paedophile hunter evidence being used to convict people of grooming (McPherson, 2020), however paedophile hunters circumvent the investigatory regulations that ensure safeguarding and sufficient acquisition of evidence (Tippett, 2022).

This chapter offered an overview of paedophile hunter discourse and the context in which PHGs conduct their work. The following chapter will be concerned with analysing the contentious aspects of paedophile hunter practice in order to mitigate negative consequences and legitimise their work in the eyes of the public and the criminal justice system.

Chapter 3: Unregulated Retribution

3.1 Introduction

This chapter will consider the problematic aspects of paedophile hunter practices and discuss the negative effects of these practices. The primary issue identified is that sting operations conducted by PHGs are recorded or live streamed and then posted online to publicly shame their target. It is argued that the genesis of paedophile hunter conduct is disintegrative shaming, which seeks to punish accused individuals extralegally through online public shaming. The disintegrative nature of this shaming creates a scenario in which accused individuals are unable to defend themselves because their social status is tarnished whether they are found guilty by a jury or not.

This chapter begins with a discussion of paedophile hunting practice and how the impacts of disintegrative shaming demonstrate this to be a problematic practice. This chapter will discuss the various rationales for PHG's recorded confrontations with their suspects and how the rationale is often used as a malleable justification of their actions. Following this, the inconsistency in paedophile hunter practice will be reviewed wherein the variance between PHGs will be compared to demonstrate the disparity of outcomes. Finally, to relate back to the research objectives, the effects of current paedophile hunter practices on the legitimacy of PHGs as a heterogeneous group will be examined in order to outline where potential improvements can be made in their practice.

3.2 Disintegrative Shaming

Braithwaite's (1989) typology of shaming presents a criteria to categorise shaming as reintegrative or stigmatic (disintegrative), for shaming to be reintegrative it must make the transgressor acknowledge their transgressive act and offer an opportunity to recompensate for their actions and reintegrate with society (McAlinden, 2005). Disintegrative shaming forgoes the latter criteria and is solely concerned with the punishment of transgressors of social norms (Robbers, 2008).

3.2.1 Online Public Shaming

Online Public Shaming (OPS) (Blitvich, 2022) is a distinctive tactic of paedophile hunting in which a PHG will record their confrontations with suspected paedophiles and post the recording on their social media page, where it is expected to be shared and reposted. This form of social sanction can be reintegrative or disintegrative depending on the execution of the sanction (Forestal, 2023; Trottier, 2020), however the primary argument of this chapter is that PHGs utilise OPS for disintegrative shaming

purposes. While there are different rationales for paedophile hunting (which will be discussed later in this chapter), PHGs employ public shaming to “degrade and ostracize the individual while reaffirming social cohesion” (Blitvich, 2022: 62).

Norlock (2017) posits that an audience is fundamental to the act of shaming, whereas Thomason (2021) saliently questions the significance of whether the audience is actual or imagined; the target will not know how widely their PHG confrontation will be shared on social media and so the consequences will be assumed to be severe regardless of the actual size of the audience of that particular PHG. Cubellis et al. (2019) support the notion that the accusation of committing sex offences will cause stigmatisation without evidence or being found guilty in court. The uncertainty of how many people have viewed the recorded confrontation, along with the assumption of guilt that accompanies an accusation, has the potential to create an intensely stigmatising effect on the target.

3.2.2 Labels and Insults

Hussey et al. (2022) conducted a cyberethnography study on two PHG social media pages and found insults and labels being used to describe suspected paedophiles such as: “beast”, “monster”, “animal” and “predator” (p.20). The use of dehumanising language is used to humiliate and stigmatise the accused individual, this reduces empathy towards the accused individual, and they are more likely to become victim to physical violence (Bilewicz and Soral, 2020). It is important to note that some PHGs declare their rationale for ‘hunting’ is child protectionism or police ineptitude, this can conceal potential ulterior motivations such as increasing the likelihood of the target experiencing physical violence. Dehumanising language consolidates the disintegrative shaming tactic, perhaps there is a desire from PHGs for the accused individual to confess to the crime and then adopt their label as a ‘predator’; however through the use of dehumanising language PHGs are communicating that they are unwilling to accept a remorseful apology and reintegrate the suspect, they wish to humiliate him.

The term ‘paedophile’ itself is popularly used by the public, which is perhaps the result of media framing of sex offenders (Blauenfeldt, 2014). It is a generalisation to label all suspects as paedophiles when in reality their paraphilic interests may be adolescent children rather than prepubescent children. This distinction is important to note because the term ‘paedophile’ conjures a stronger negative social reaction than would be the case if the suspect were more accurately labelled a hebephile (Jahnke et al., 2022), this negative reaction is undoubtedly influenced by media representations of paedophilia (Harris and Socia, 2016). The term ‘paedophile hunter’ mobilises the public’s fear and disgust towards paedophiles (Lehmann et al., 2020) in order to garner support for the PHG cause.

3.2.3 The Impacts of Disintegrative Shaming

Disintegrative shaming frustrates sex offenders' attempts to reintegrate into society (Harper et al., 2024), furthermore disintegrative shaming can counterproductively drive deviant behaviours 'underground' (Murphy and Kiffin-Petersen, 2017). Suppressing deviant behaviours and paraphilic interests can generate a higher risk as the suspect can continue their behaviour with more diligence and become less likely to seek help in fear of further marginalisation (Schultz, 2014). Eroding the social capital of suspected paedophiles excludes them from social normality, which can increase the opportunity for reoffending behaviours (Grossi, 2017).

An individual's social identity is compromised by stigmatic labels, being publicly labelled as a paedophile can result in humiliation, isolation, breakdown of relationships and loss of employment (Gordon, 2013; Grossi, 2017; Levenson, 2011; Levenson and Cotter, 2005; Schultz, 2014). Cubellis et al. (2019) posit that individuals who are only accused of sex offences, rather than prosecuted for sex offences, are at a much higher risk of experiencing violence because they still have to live and work in the community in which they have been accused, where they can be targeted by vigilantes and experience threats and violence. Reintegration post-shaming can be extremely difficult, even more so when housing and employment restrictions can be put in place through civil orders (CPS, 2021). The sex offender label is deleterious to one's self-esteem and mental health, this is even more pervasive when labelled a paedophile, which can negatively affect attempts to rehabilitate (Robbers, 2008). It is worth noting that for some PHGs and their audiences, the retributive tactic of OPS may be a positive quality that they perceive to be a more effective punishment than would be prescribed by the criminal justice system.

As discussed earlier in this chapter, mental health can be significantly impacted when one is publicly accused of being a paedophile, creating a greater risk of self-harm and suicide (Cohen et al., 2019). This means that the accused individual (who is potentially innocent) may kill themselves before going to trial, which undermines due process; but also that a potentially guilty child groomer may escape justice by killing themselves prior to being found guilty and receiving a court ordered punishment. If the aim of paedophile hunting is justice then disintegrative shaming fails to dispense this; if the aim of paedophile hunting is prevention of future offences then perhaps disintegrative shaming is fulfilling this role, potentially at the cost of some innocent men committing suicide.

3.2.4 Inconsistent Investigatory Practices

A common theme of this research has been the heterogeneity of paedophile hunters and how their methods of investigation vary considerably between PHGs. The disparity in the severity of methods

used by PHGs means that PHGs are inconsistently applying their own notions of justice, which serves to undermine the criminal justice system and jeopardise their legitimisation as a public service.

3.2.5 Undermining the Criminal Justice System

Frampton's (2021) work on criminal justice practitioners' attitudes towards paedophile hunters highlights that many practitioners view paedophile hunters as antithetical to values of policing (Purshouse, 2020) and they doubt that collaboration between the police and PHGs is possible (Hadjimatheou, 2019). Collaboration may be unlikely for the foreseeable future, yet it is crucial to scrutinise paedophile hunter practice as they will continue to operate laterally to the criminal justice system. There is no uniform code of investigation that all PHGs adhere to, unlike the police, which creates a contrast in how the police and PHGs investigate (McPherson, 2020); in order for PHGs to be legitimised they also should have a standardised investigation process similar to the RIPA regulations that the police are bound by.

The heterogenic nature of PHGs means that there is no established standardised code of practice among hunters because they operate independently with their own motivations and justifications. This variance in practice allows some groups to operate as valuable intelligence resources for the police and other groups to act as vigilantes dispensing their own disparate form of justice through OPS (Purshouse, 2020). The variation in practices between different groups is informed by different justifications for 'hunting', as will be discussed later in this chapter. Purshouse (2020) notes one example of variance in PHG practice, particularly that some groups use images of adults for their decoy profiles, which increases the complexity of the court case unnecessarily as it makes it harder to prove that the target was intending to meet a child. As a result of a lack of standardised practice among PHGs there is consequently an absence of transparency or accountability in their methods of investigation and their behaviour towards their targets. Seemingly the only occasions in which PHGs are held to account for their actions are situations where the paedophile hunters have committed crimes such as assault or kidnapping during their sting operations (Favarel-Garrigues, 2019; BBC News, 2023; Rowe, 2015). Paedophile hunting is a quasi-legal activity, the act itself is legally permissible despite being disapproved of by criminal justice institutions (Gillespie, 2019), yet currently the only way to hold PHGs to account is to arrest them for criminal acts executed during their sting operations.

3.2.6 Doxing

Another issue with PHG practice relates to doxing and online shaming. One aim of OPS is to encourage the PHG's audience to engage with the content through likes, comments and shares (Trottier, 2020).

PHG's can weaponise the visibility of the suspect through doxing their private information in order to commission their audience to harass, threaten, and physical attack the target (Douglas, 2016; Citron, 2014). This is problematic because doxing is utilised as a shaming tool to inflict fear and embarrassment on the target without the target being found guilty in court, this undermines the role of the police by dispensing their own version of justice through extralegally imposed sanctions that unduly villainises the target.

Doxing is often executed on faulty intelligence resulting in getting the wrong addresses and misidentifying suspects, this has led to the victimisation of innocent people (Cubellis et al., 2019; Eysen, 2001). Faulty intelligence is a consequence of lack of a standardised practice among PHGs and their interpretation of evidentiary boundaries (Noble, 2017). Posting recorded confrontations online along with the personal information of the target is a characteristic component of many PHG investigations; however the timescale in which they post the confrontation is significant to discuss. Some PHG's opt to livestream their sting operations, some choose to record the confrontations and post it online prior to the suspect's trial, and some choose to wait until the suspect has been found guilty before posting the confrontation. The timescale in which PHG's publish confrontation recordings has an enormous impact on the wellbeing of the suspect (discussed below) and can undermine due process when sting operations go viral on social media.

3.2.7 The Side Effect of Recorded Confrontations

Across the literature there are a multitude of examples of suicides caused by misidentification of suspects through poor investigation techniques from PHGs and unjust infamy caused through online public shaming via posted confrontations on social media (Noble, 2017; Purshouse, 2020; Booth, 2013; Trottier, 2017; Tippett, 2022; De Rond et al., 2021). As previously mentioned, disintegrative shaming can have deleterious effects on the mental health of the stigmatised, and suicidal ideation is a common by-product of paedophile hunter investigations due to the stress of being accused of sexual offences (Key et al., 2021). When a suspect commits suicide prior to their case being heard in court it highlights some concerns, those being: if the suspect was found guilty then he had escaped justice, likewise if the suspect was found innocent then the paedophile hunters should be held accountable for playing a contributory role in the suspect's suicide. In this way, paedophile hunter investigations undermine the criminal justice system and delegitimises PHGs through investigatory failures.

Doxing suspected paedophiles is a phenomenally problematic aspect of paedophile hunter practice. The families of accused individuals are exposed to 'courtesy stigma' (Goffman, 1963) or secondary

stigmatisation (Hadjimatheou 2019; Evans et al., 2021; Cubellis et al., 2019) where they will also feel ostracised and humiliated, and are sometimes ridiculed or attacked for their association with their 'exposed' family member (Phillips and Gates, 2011). The families of suspected paedophiles are unfairly considered as collateral damage in PHG sting operations and are the subject of unwarranted stigmatisation.

3.3 The Flawed Rationales of Recorded Confrontations

As discussed earlier in this chapter, disintegrative shaming is a key outcome of paedophile hunter practice; despite the predictably stigmatising result of their work, the heterogeneity of paedophile hunters means that PHGs may justify their methods of investigation in various ways which creates an ethical disparity. This section will discuss various possible justifications of recorded confrontations.

3.3.1 Public Protection

Some PHGs claim that they record encounters with their targets as a form of public notification in order to prevent the target from grooming more children; however the result of this OPS is typically delegitimising (Douglas, 2016) and invites harassment and violence from the paedophile hunter's supporters and audience. The amount of harassment and threats of violence the target experiences could be a PHGs internal measure of a successful shaming.

The criminal justice system imposes legal sanctions against sex offenders, such as Sexual Harm Prevention Orders (CPS, 2024) under the rationale of public protection. Similarly, paedophile hunters impose social sanctions with the same rationale of public protection; however PHGs do this through decimation of the social status of the suspect and public notification of their dangerousness (Anderson and Wood, 2021). Posting recordings of sting operations online could be considered a disproportionate sanction because disintegrative shaming is antagonistic to the rehabilitation of sex offenders (Harper et al., 2024) and thus shaming is a short-term deterrence strategy that ultimately undermines the public protection rationale in the long-term (Tippett, 2022).

3.3.2 'We're recording for your own protection and ours'

Some PHGs record confrontations to provide evidence that they have not harmed or entrapped their target, similar reasoning is used for police body worn cameras. A key difference between PHG recorded confrontations and police body worn camera footage is that the bodycam footage is for internal use only with the exception of it being used as evidence in court (Walton and Penfold, 2023). This

justification for recorded confrontations is a positive measure to ensure the safety of both the target and the PHG, however the ethical principles of this justification are easily tarnished when the recording is posted online. Recorded confrontations are typically made with the intention of posting it online to gain the attention of the public, which can potentially compromise the impartiality of the jury if the case is heard in court. The protection of the 'hunters' and the 'hunted' comes at the cost of the protection of potential future victims by corrupting the court case and letting the suspect walk free.

3.3.3 Recording for the Purposes of Gaining a Confession

Some PHGs use recorded confrontations as a means for the suspect to confess to attempting to meet an underage child following sexual grooming. Offering the opportunity for the suspect to explain themselves can elicit a confession from the suspect which could logically aid the prosecution case against them. However, Hussey et al. (2022) comment that if the chatlogs obtained by paedophile hunters are given to the police as evidence of the suspect attempting to groom a child, then the recorded confrontation is not justified as further evidence of a confession but rather used as a means to shame the suspect. When confessions are made to paedophile hunters, they are often disbelieved, rejected, and met with insults. Atonement is not the objective of recorded confrontations, but rather it is argued that retributive shaming (Anderson and Wood, 2021) of the suspect is the aim of confrontations - often as a form of entertainment for the audience.

PHGs may record confrontations with suspected paedophiles for entertainment purposes, exemplified by the television programme 'To Catch a Predator' (Kohm, 2009). Insults and humiliation tactics are sometimes used during confrontations (discussed earlier in this chapter) as a catharsis for the paedophile hunters and their audience, it could be argued that insulting and belittling the suspect is for the purpose of punitive entertainment in order to gain more attention to their social media pages (De Rond et al., 2021). It is notable that PHGs may conceal this justification for recorded confrontations, yet it is implicit in their behaviour towards suspects that humiliation is a feature of the confrontation stage of their investigation.

3.5 Conclusion and Effects on Legitimacy

Paedophile hunters typically use controversial tactics such as decoys, live streaming and online public shaming which are ultimately informed by disintegrative shaming. Disintegrative shaming is seemingly employed as a deterrence to prevent other people from grooming children (Finnemore and Hollis, 2020) however Purshouse (2020) stipulates that the deterrent effect of OPS has yet to be empirically proven. Recorded confrontations are a problematic aspect of paedophile hunter practice regardless of

how or when the PHG chooses to implement them, it would seem that recorded confrontations would only be suitable conduct if used as evidence in court rather than posted online as a deterrence or as entertainment for their audience. While some PHGs aim to secure convictions through the collection of quality evidence, some PHGs are more radical in their shaming ethos and adopt OPS as the desired outcome of their investigation. This disparity in the methods of investigation is the main source of differentiation in the legitimacy of PHGs.

In order to increase their organisational legitimacy PHGs must ensure congruence between the social implications of their investigations and the accepted norms of society (Dowling and Pfeffer, 1975), by limiting the negative outcomes of their practice PHGs may be more widely perceived as providing a valuable public service (Suchman, 1995). Mazerolle et al. (2013) systematically reviewed police interventions and proposed that in order for the police to increase their legitimacy they must apply principles of procedural justice (citizen participation, neutrality, respect, and trustworthiness) in any and all encounters with citizens (Tyler and Fagan, 2008). These principles of procedural justice could be applied to paedophile hunting to legitimise the practice in the eyes of the of state actors and of the public. The following chapter will be concerned with establishing a code of conduct for paedophile hunters to conduct their investigations in a manner that upholds ethical principles and improves the perceived legitimacy of PHG practices.

Chapter 4: A Harm Reduction Approach To Paedophile Hunting

4.1 Introduction

The likelihood of collaboration between the criminal justice system and PHGs is slim, however improving PHG practices could strengthen the relationship between them. This is important because the evidence that PHGs obtain can be effective to secure convictions. A strained relationship already currently exists between PHGs and the police, yet strengthening the relationships could be a positive development that helps the two to achieve the shared goal of child protection.

Paedophile hunting was born from a perceived systematic failure to protect children, this systematic failure can begin to be addressed by PHGs acting as a supplementary information sources to police investigations. In order for future collaboration to be recognised, PHG investigations needs to be consistent, accurate and humane. The heterogeneity of PHGs has been discussed throughout this project and many groups may not wish to professionalise their work, with this in mind this chapter is concerned with establishing a Harm Reduction Approach (HRA) for paedophile hunters that wish to professionalise their work and ameliorate the delegitimising aspects of current paedophile hunter practices. Hypothetically there will be a hierarchal distinction between paedophile hunters who choose to adopt a HRA in their investigation and those that do not in the way their organisational legitimacy is perceived by the public and the criminal justice system.

As non-state actors, paedophile hunters are not bound to RIPA 2000 rules and do not have to abide by PACE codes as the police do (Walton and Penfold, 2023); however the lack of a standardised code of practice has created a huge variance in the professionalism and legitimacy of different PHGs. This chapter seeks to address this issue by outlining improvements that could legitimise current paedophile hunter practices.

4.2 Improving the Quality of Evidence

In order to improve the consistency of PHG investigations, the role of the paedophile hunter should be oriented around assembling evidence that is admissible in court and will aid the prosecution in securing a conviction. Where a PHG has successfully provided evidence that led to a conviction, other PHGs may learn from these cases to understand the evidentiary standard they must attain prior to handing

evidence to the police. Purshouse (2020) notes that amendments to s.15 of the Sexual Offences Act 2003, 'attempting to meet a child following sexual grooming', has been more narrowly defined since the Criminal Attempts Act 1981 and broadened the actus reus for the offence to encompass a single communication with a child. Despite the broadened actus reus, it would benefit paedophile hunters to ensure their portfolio of evidence (mainly chatlogs and images sent within chatlogs) clearly demonstrates that: (1) the suspect was sexually grooming the decoy and (2) intended to meet with the decoy in order to sexually abuse them. Ensuring PHG evidence can demonstrate these two acts will clarify the intentions of the suspect when tried in court (*Corpus Delicti*) and help to secure conviction (Moran, 2003).

The scope for interpretations about the admissibility of evidence needs to be minimised within PHGs, paedophile hunters must compare the quality of evidence gathered in chatlogs to an evidentiary specification as described above. Where paedophile hunters use their interpretation of the quality of their evidence it increases the risk of insufficient evidence being delivered in court and nullifies their work, potentially allowing a guilty man to go unpunished.

It is important that paedophile hunters reevaluate certain processes of their investigations to ensure the intentions of the suspect are clear when the trial is heard in court. For example, decoy profiles should not depict adults and should ensure that those they are speaking with are notified of the decoy's under-age status as soon as possible in the conversation (Purshouse, 2020). Decoys should also never initiate the first contact with their targets to avoid claims that they were enticed or entrapped by the paedophile hunter. Hypothetically, if paedophile hunters reorient their current practice to emphasise their digital investigations and gather high quality evidence then the risk of harm to the suspect and their family is reduced, and the pragmatic legitimacy of paedophile hunters (Suchman, 1995) will increase as they will be seen to provide a valuable social function that achieves practical outcomes.

4.3 Recording Confrontations

The ethical approach to paedophile hunting that this project proposes would focus on digital investigations, as discussed previously in this chapter, and forgo sting operations and recorded confrontations. Despite discouragement from the police and CPS, it is apparent that these aspects of paedophile hunting are considered integral to many paedophile hunters and as such recommendations should be made to improve this practice to reduce the likelihood of harm when this practice manifests instead of blanket discouragement which has thus far been an unsuccessful deterrent for paedophile hunters.

Recorded sting operations could generate supplementary evidence in addition to chatlog evidence which can assist in the prosecution of their target. The evidence gained through recorded confrontation can bolster the case against the suspect by proving the suspect had attempted to meet a child following sexual grooming. However, recorded confrontations should not be posted online under any circumstances to prevent contravention of due process. As discussed in the previous chapter, many key issues with PHGs highlighted in the literature stem from online public shaming, issues such as: the disintegrative shaming motive (Hussey et al., 2022), undermining due process, permanent record of the confrontation (Purshouse, 2020), and the disproportionately severe treatment of suspects (Sorell, 2019). These issues would be pacified if the recorded confrontations were not posted online, particularly live streams. Recorded confrontations could function similarly to police body worn cameras, to protect the PHG and the target from false claims of assault or blackmail and to be used as further evidence in court. Furthermore, this evidence need not be collected by paedophile hunters at all but rather PHGs could supply the police with chatlog evidence, a scheduled sting date and an image of the suspect and allow the police to effectively sting the suspect instead of the PHG. This would not be as self-gratifying for the PHG but the result of an improved likelihood of conviction would surely outweigh the PHG's need for recognition; unless the PHG's sole motivation is social media engagement.

Many PHGs post the recorded confrontations with suspects online on their social media pages, this could be perceived as self-gratification under the guise of disintegrative shaming by posting stings as a form of entertainment to their audiences (Kohm, 2009). The necessity for recognition of the paedophile hunters' work should be secondary to their goal of child protection, for this reason paedophile hunters should relinquish the in-person sting operations and OPS side of their practice. Posting these recordings online as a social sanction should not be the goal of paedophile hunting as it is a short-sighted victory; paedophile hunters should orient themselves towards gathering quality evidence in order to secure convictions against their targets because sex offender registration is a much longer-term sanction than being shamed online.

4.4 Doxing

For paedophile hunters that wish to reduce the potential for harm in their practice, doxing their suspects is an unsuitable practice. Douglas (2016) states that doxing can be justified if establishing somebody's identity is in the public's interest, however the author stipulates this by stating that this only applies if the benefit of publicly exposing an individual's identity outweighs the potential harm to the individual. Doxing causes undue stress on the innocent families of PHG suspects and puts them at risk of harassment and assault for simply being associated with the suspect, this secondary

stigmatisation is a collateral effect of doxing (Evans et al., 2024). Doxing also increases the risk of the suspect committing suicide prior to their case being heard in court (Cohen et al., 2019) due to the reputational damage already being done, this type of harm is irreversible which is why this practice must be ceased as part of a harm reduction approach. If a HRA is adopted by PHGs then the personal information of PHG targets should no longer be posted online, the severe consequences of doxing for the suspect and their family make it an unethical practice for paedophile hunters to engage in.

In the next portion of this chapter, I will propose an alternative practice to sting operations and recorded confrontations in the form of written post-trial reports; in this report it would be ethically viable to publish the full name of the suspect as this will be publicly available online from the court listings, however this should be the only identifier of the suspect made in the report in order to protect the identity of the suspect and their family and limit the possibility of vigilante justice occurring.

4.5 Publishing Post-Trial Reports

The most significant proposal of this project is an ethical alternative to current paedophile hunter practice in the form of post-trial reports written by paedophile hunters. This report could be published whether the suspect is found innocent or guilty as the intention of this report is to make the evidence publicly available. Publishing a post-trial report will allow the paedophile hunters to fully document their actions during the investigation of their suspects, including a full transcript of chatlog evidence and a transcript of the recorded confrontation if one takes place; supplementary information could be added alongside the chatlogs such as noting the number of occasions where the decoy's underage status is mentioned or noting where the PHG has encouraged sexually driven conversations and for what purpose.

It is worth noting that it's possible that the reason OPS is favoured over post-trial reporting is because OPS enables the PHG to gain engagement on social media through likes and shares and essentially take credit for the conviction to boost further engagement on their social media page. It is possible that there will be a divide between paedophile hunters that adopt the tactic of post-trial reporting in order to reduce harm and increase legitimacy and those that maintain current practice. Potentially the typology of PHGs will be informed by who they are aiming to be perceived as legitimate by; semi-professional PHGs may wish to be perceived as legitimate by the state, PHGs that operate for social media engagement may wish to be legitimate in the eyes of their audience, and PHGs that operate solely to shame their targets may not strive for any form of legitimacy.

This alternative practice may be unattractive to some PHGs; however it is argued that adopting post-trial reporting as the primary shaming mechanism will alleviate some ethical concerns around their current practices. The potential benefits to this alternative practice will be discussed below.

4.6 Transparency and Accountability

Publishing post-trial reports that document any information that the PHG has submitted as evidence enables the public to analyse the veracity of the jury's verdict, whether innocent or guilty, and creates a record of the suspect's actions if they are involved in future offences. These reports could be used in future court proceedings if the suspect is found innocent on this occasion but is accused of similar offences in the future. Making evidence publicly available increases the transparency of the PHG and has the potential to introduce a reintegrative shaming element through publicly acknowledging the wrongdoing of the suspect and subsequently punishing the suspect through legal sanctions rather than social sanctions.

Burlea and Popa (2013) assert that to establish and maintain legitimacy, organisations must disclose information along with "actions realized in compliance with social and environmental norms and values." (p.1579). In order for paedophile hunters to increase their legitimacy they must be transparent and accountable. Paedophile hunters publishing written reports that detail their actions during the investigation of their target can allow their methods of investigation to be scrutinised and audited (Dennis, 2015) by the public, the criminal justice system, and other PHGs. This will increase the accountability of the PHG and ensures their methods of evidence collection and handling are ethically and legally sufficient.

4.7 Harm Reduction

Post-trial reporting is a more ethical alternative to disintegrative shaming through OPS and doxing that still exposes the suspect's online grooming and CSE but focuses on the conviction as a measure of success rather than disintegrative shaming as a measure of success. The feasibility of these reports to reduce harm comparatively to current PHG practice could be measured through the reduction in cases of violence or harassment against suspects and their families and reduction in suicides related to paedophile hunter investigations. The suspect will no longer be publicly outed as a paedophile before they have stood trial for their offence, this could hypothetically reduce the likelihood of suicidal ideation in the suspect, and in any case once the suspect has been arrested it is the police's responsibility to monitor wellbeing.

The report will create a platform for evidence of the suspect's behaviour to be exposed while protecting the personal information of the suspect. As mentioned previously, the only identifying information that should be included in the report is information that is available throughout the trial and in court listings. The adherence to protecting the personal information, other than full name of the suspect, protects the identities of the suspect's family to prevent secondary stigmatisation which often invites harassment and violence (Phillips and Gates, 2011).

4.8 Protecting Due Process

Publishing reports after the trial has concluded will not undermine the principle of due process because the suspect will have been granted a fair trial (Article 6 of ECHR) as there is no potential that the jury has been exposed to the recorded confrontation being posted online by the PHG (Welsh et al., 2021). This is an important concern to address, as undermining the criminal justice system is a delegitimising aspect of paedophile hunting. PHGs will increase their perceived legitimacy through mitigating contentious aspects of their practice and highlighting the value they bring as service providers. By removing the disintegrative shaming component of paedophile hunting, it could establish PHGs as intelligence organisations as opposed to vigilantes in the eyes of the police and CPS.

4.9 Conclusion

This chapter has been concerned with answering the second research question by proposing improvements to paedophile hunter practice in order to reduce harm and improve legitimacy. The major recommendations discussed in this chapter were to: cease posting recorded confrontations online, refrain from doxing, and to reorient paedophile hunting to focus on digital investigations that provide accurate high-quality evidence. This chapter entailed a further recommendation of alternative practice by means of paedophile hunters writing and publishing post-trial reports on their investigations and findings. Admittedly this recommended practice is rudimentary as it has yet to be explored or tested, but the potential benefits of reformation of paedophile hunter practice could be ample.

One concern highlighted in the previous chapter was that paedophile hunting may undermine principles of the criminal justice system; in this chapter it is recommended that paedophile hunters desist from posting confrontations online as it bypasses the need for due process by presuming the suspect is guilty before their trial. It is important to note that one could argue that by conducting covert investigations without authorisation from the state, PHGs are still undermining the police as an institution. This concern cannot be easily addressed, as paedophile hunting fundamentally relies on covert investigations to obtain evidence to provide to the police. However if PHGs were solely

interested in digital investigation and evidence collection then their role could be perceived as supplementary to the police rather than competitive. The question remains: can a PHG ever be perceived as a legitimate organisation, by the public and by the police, if they are seen to be undermining the role of the police? And if not, then can PHGs continue to work laterally with the police with a working relationship or must paedophile hunting be outlawed?

Chapter 5: Conclusion

This research paper aimed to identify the problematic and delegitimising aspects of paedophile hunter practices. This project found that paedophile hunters currently operate as unregulated organisations that lack accountability and transparency, who extralegally conduct covert investigations without a code of conduct in place to safeguard themselves and those they investigate (Purshouse, 2020). Paedophile hunters are often considered problematic by the criminal justice system and the public because their current investigatory practices undermine the role of the police and jeopardise the due process model that ensures impartial trials (Hadjimatheou, 2019). The literature indicates that paedophile hunting is a response to a perceived vacuum of police effectiveness (Silke, 2001), yet the techniques in which paedophile hunters conduct their investigations are so dissimilar to the police that they are a cause for concern. Paedophile hunting as a response to police ineffectiveness creates a division between PHGs, those that wish to mirror the role of the police and those that wish to work laterally with no code of conduct or overarching ethos.

The heterogeneity of PHGs means that each group operates with different motivations, methods, and desired results. The variation in techniques of investigation means that PHGs operate with varying levels of professionalism and legitimacy. The evidence collection role of paedophile hunting seems to be a legitimising aspect to their work as they are providing a public service by aiding the prosecution of sex offenders (Tippett, 2022). However, the majority of PHGs engage in delegitimising practices such as online public shaming and doxing in order to humiliate their target and incite harassment and violence. The broad variation within PHGs warrants further research, it would benefit the literature on paedophile hunting to typologically examine PHGs in order to classify groups by their motivations, desired results, methods, professionalism, and their relationship with the criminal justice system. This research would be of benefit to lawmakers in how they legislate the activities of paedophile hunters as it is still considered to be a grey area.

This research paper found that one of the most striking characteristics of paedophile hunting is disintegrative shaming (Braithewaite, 1989) through online public shaming; though sting operations, decoys, and recorded confrontations are also emblematic of paedophile hunting. Disintegrative shaming in the form of online public humiliation and doxing problematically undermines the judicial system by assuming the target to be guilty before standing trial, furthermore when recorded confrontations are posted online it risks tainting the impartiality of the jury (Purshouse, 2020). The

disintegrative shaming practices of paedophile hunters increases the potential harm to their targets and the target's families; this harm is disproportionate to the benefits of online shaming and thus the tactic should be abandoned in favour of a tactic that achieves the goals of the organisation. This project also proposed alternative practices for paedophile hunters to investigate suspected paedophiles in a way that legitimises PHGs through a harm reduction approach that emphasises conviction as the desired result rather than public ostracization (Hadjimatheou, 2019). The harm reduction strategy proposed in this project places greater emphasis on the evidence collection role that PHGs currently engage in, while desisting from disintegrative shaming practices such as doxing and online public shaming. The core proposition of this harm reduction strategy was to replace these delegitimising practices with post-trial reporting to allow the evidence that the PHG gathered to be highlighted while preventing harm to the target of their investigation. It is hoped that by proposing improvements to PHG practice, the conversation around the legitimacy of paedophile hunting will become nuanced instead of dismissing their cause as vigilantism.

Case Reference List

R v Walters [T20167262] (Newcastle Crown Court, 6th April, 2017)

R v Ali case [T20160897] (Newcastle Crown Court, 6th April, 2017)

Sutherland (Appellant) v Her Majesty's Advocate (Respondent) (Scotland) [2020] UKSC 32

Reference List

Adler, A. (2001). The Perverse Law of Child Pornography. *Columbia Law Review*, 101(2), pp.209–273. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/1123799> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Allison, R. (2000). Doctor driven out of home by vigilantes. *The Guardian*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/uk/2000/aug/30/childprotection.society> (Accessed: 14/11/2024)

Anderson, B. and Wood, M. A. (2021). Doxing: A scoping review and typology. In: J. Bailey, A. Flynn, & N. Henry (Eds.), *The Emerald international handbook of technology-facilitated violence and abuse*, pp. 205–226. Emerald Publishing. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-83982-848-520211015> (Accessed: 10/01/2025)

BBC News. (2019). Police concerns over rise of “paedophile hunters.”. *BBC News*. [Online] November 6. Available at: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-england-50302912> (Accessed: 19/10/2024)

BBC News. (2023). North East “paedophile hunters” first to face prison sentences. [Online]. June 23rd. Available at: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-england-tyne-66001438> (Accessed: 09/01/2025)

Bell, V. (2002). The vigilant (e) parent and the paedophile: The News of the World campaign 2000 and the contemporary governmentality of child sexual abuse. *Feminist Theory*, 3(1), pp.83–102. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1460012002003001068> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Bilewicz, M. and Soral, W. (2020). Hate speech epidemic. The dynamic effects of derogatory language on intergroup relations and political radicalization. *Political Psychology*, 41(S1), pp.3–33. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/pops.12670> (Accessed: 12/12/24)

Blauenfeldt, A. (2015). *Violent Rapists and Depraved Paedophiles: Linguistic Representation of Sex Offenders in the British Tabloid Press-A Comparative Corpus-Based Study*. [Bachelor’s Thesis]. Malmö University. [Online] Available at: <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1481740/FULLTEXT01.pdf> (Accessed: 27/02/2025)

Blitvich, P. G. (2022). Moral emotions, good moral panics, social regulation, and online public shaming. *Language & Communication*, 84, pp.61–75. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.langcom.2022.02.002> (Accessed: 12/12/24)

Booth, R. (2013). Vigilante paedophile hunters ruining lives with internet stings. *The Guardian*. [Online]. November 30th. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2013/oct/25/vigilante-paedophile-hunters-online-police> (Accessed: 09/01/2025)

Braithwaite, J. (1989). *Crime, shame and reintegration*. New York: Cambridge University Press.

Bruns, A. (2017). Echo chamber? What echo chamber? Reviewing the evidence. In *6th Biennial Future of Journalism Conference (FOJ17)*, 2017-09-14 - 2017-09-15. (Unpublished). [Online] Available at: https://eprints.qut.edu.au/113937/8/Echo_Chamber.pdf (Accessed: 31/10/2024)

Burlea, A.S. and Popa, I. (2013). Legitimacy theory. In: Idowu, S.O., Capaldi, N., Zu, L., Gupta, A.D. (eds). *Encyclopaedia of Corporate Social Responsibility*. Springer: Berlin. [Online] Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-28036-8_471 (Accessed: 23/01/2025)

Butler, A. E., Copnell, B. and Hall, H. (2017). Researching people who are bereaved: Managing risks to participants and researchers. *Nursing Ethics*, 26(1), pp.224–234. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0969733017695656> (Accessed: 21/11/2024)

Campbell, E. (2016). Policing paedophilia: Assembling bodies, spaces and things. *Crime, Media, Culture: An International Journal*, 12(3), pp.345–365. [Online] Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1741659015623598> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Casey, L. (2023). *An independent review into the standards of behaviour and internal culture of the Metropolitan Police Service*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.met.police.uk/SysSiteAssets/media/downloads/met/about-us/baroness-casey-review/update-march-2023/baroness-casey-review-march-2023a.pdf> (Accessed: 13/11/2024)

Chang, L. Y. C. and Poon, R. (2017). Internet Vigilantism: Attitudes and Experiences of University Students Toward Cyber Crowdsourcing in Hong Kong. *International journal of offender therapy and comparative criminology*, 61(16), pp.1912–1932. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306624X16639037> (Accessed: 31/10/2024)

Chang, L. Y. C., Zhong, L. Y. and Grabosky, P. N. (2016). Citizen co-production of cyber security: Self-help, vigilantes, and cybercrime. *Regulation & Governance*, 12(1), pp.101–114. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/rego.12125> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Chiang, E., De Rond, M. and Lok, J. (2023). Identity in a Self-styled 'Paedophile-hunting' Group: A Linguistic Analysis of Stance in Facebook Group Chats. *Applied linguistics*, 45(4), pp.599-620. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/amad034>. (Accessed 18/10/2024)

Citron, D. K. (2014). *Hate crimes in cyberspace*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

Cohen, L.J., Wilman-Depena, S., Barzilay, S., Hawes, M., Yaseen, Z. and Galynker, I. (2019). Correlates of Chronic Suicidal Ideation Among Community-Based Minor-Attracted Persons. *Sexual Abuse*, 32(3), pp.273–300. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1079063219825868>. (Accessed: 16/01/2025)

CPS. (2021). Rape and Sexual Offences - Chapter 15: Sexual Harm Prevention Orders (SHPOS). *The Crown Prosecution Service*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.cps.gov.uk/legal-guidance/rape-and-sexual-offences-chapter-15-sexual-harm-prevention-orders-shpos> (Accessed: 13/03/2025)

CPS. (2022). Online Child Abuse Activist Groups on the internet. *Crown Prosecution Service*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.cps.gov.uk/legal-guidance/online-child-abuse-activist-groups-internet> (Accessed: 19/10/2024)

CPS. (2024). Rape and Sexual Offences - Chapter 15: Sexual Harm Prevention Orders (SHPOs). *The Crown Prosecution Service*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.cps.gov.uk/legal-guidance/rape-and-sexual-offences-chapter-15-sexual-harm-prevention-orders-shpos> (Accessed 07/04/2025)

Critcher, C. (2002). Media, Government and Moral Panic: the politics of paedophilia in Britain 2000-1. *Journalism Studies*, 3(4), pp. 521–535. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1461670022000019182> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Critcher, C. (2009). Widening The Focus: Moral Panics as Moral Regulation. *British Journal of Criminology*, 49(1), pp.17–34. [Online] Available at: <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1093/bjc/azn040> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Cubellis, M. A., Evans, D. N., and Fera, A. G. (2019). Sex Offender Stigma: An Exploration of Vigilantism against Sex Offenders. *Deviant Behavior*, 40(2), pp.225–239. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01639625.2017.1420459> (Accessed: 12/12/24)

Cunningham, E. (2023). Three criminals in police uniform: Reflections on radical feminist insight to challenge misogyny in policing. *Journal of Legal, Ethical and Regulatory Issues*, 27(2), pp.1-13. [Online] Available at: <https://www.abacademies.org/articles/three-criminals-in-police-uniform-reflections-on-radical-feminist-insight-to-challenge-misogyny-in-policing.pdf> (Accessed: 13/11/2024)

Deflem, M. (2016). Introduction: the perpetual politics of policing. in Deflem, M. (Ed.), *The Politics of Policing: Between Force and Legitimacy, Sociology of Crime, Law and Deviance, Vol. 21*, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, Leeds. pp. xiii-xvi. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/S1521-613620160000021019> (Accessed: 13/01/2025)

Dennis, I. (2015). *Auditing Theory*. London: Routledge. [Online] Available at: https://alitsaki.ir/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/4_5965290204947285263.pdf (Accessed: 07/04/2025)

De Rond, M., Lok, J. and Marrison, A. (2021). To catch a predator: the lived experience of extreme practices. *Academy of Management Journal*, 65(3), pp.870–902. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2020.1492> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Douglas, D. M. (2016). Doxing: a conceptual analysis. *Ethics and Information Technology*, 18(3), pp.199–210. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10676-016-9406-0> (Accessed: 10/01/2025)

Dowling, J. and Pfeffer, J. (1975). Organizational Legitimacy: Social Values and Organizational Behavior. *The Pacific Sociological Review*, 18(1), pp.122–136. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/1388226>. (Accessed: 16/01/2025)

Drucker, A.M., Fleming, P. and Chan, A. (2016). Research techniques made simple: assessing risk of bias in systematic reviews. *Journal of Investigative Dermatology*, 136(11), pp.109–114. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jid.2016.08.021> (Accessed: 21/11/2024)

Dunsby, R. M. and Howes, L. M. (2018). The NEW adventures of the digital vigilante! Facebook users' views on online naming and shaming. *Australian & New Zealand Journal of Criminology*, 52(1), pp.41–59. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0004865818778736> (Accessed: 31/10/2024)

Evans, D., Trahan, A., and Laird, K. (2021). Shame and blame: Secondary stigma among families of convicted sex offenders. *Criminology & Criminal Justice*, 23(1), pp.78–97. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/17488958211017391> (Accessed: 12/12/24)

Evans, J. (2003). Vigilance and vigilantes. *Theoretical Criminology*, 7(2), pp.163–189. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362480603007002416> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Eyssen, A.B. (2001). Does Community Notification for Sex Offenders Violate the Eighth Amendment's Prohibition against Cruel and Unusual Punishment - A Focus on Vigilantism Resulting from Megan's Law. *St. Mary's Law Journal*, 33, pp.102-142. [Online] Available at:

<https://commons.stmarytx.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2303&context=thestmaryslawjournal> (Accessed: 15/11/24)

Favarel-Garrigues, G. (2019). Digital vigilantism and anti-paedophile activism in Russia. Between civic involvement in law enforcement, moral policing and business venture. *Global Crime*, 21(3–4), pp.306–326. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17440572.2019.1676738> (Accessed: 09/01/2025)

Finnemore, M. and Hollis, D. B. (2020). Beyond naming and shaming: Accusations and international law in cybersecurity. *European Journal of International Law*, 31(3), pp.969–1003. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/ejil/chaa056> (Accessed: 10/01/2025)

Forestal, J. (2023). Social media, social control, and the politics of public shaming. *American Political Science Review*, 118(4), pp.1704–1718. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0003055423001053> (Accessed: 12/12/24)

Frampton, L. (2021). *The Hunters and The Hunted. Exploring Practitioner and Public Attitudes Towards Paedophile Hunting Groups and the Implications for Risk Management*. PhD. Thesis. University of Portsmouth. [Online] Available at: https://pure.port.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/27089150/The_Hunters_and_The_Hunted._Exploring_Practitioner_and_Public_Attitudes_Towards_Paedophile_Hunting_Groups_and_the_Implications_for_Risk_Management.pdf (Accessed: 31/10/2024)

Frampton, L. (2022). ‘Paedophile Hunters’: Practitioner Perspectives. *Probation Journal*, 70(2), pp.143–159. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/02645505211070084> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Furedi, F. (2002) *Culture of fear: Risk-taking and the morality of low expectation*. London: Continuum.

Gillespie, A.A. (2019). “Paedophile Hunters”: How Should the Law Respond?. *Criminal Law Review*, (12), pp.1016–1034. [Online] Available at: https://eprints.lancs.ac.uk/id/eprint/137364/2/Paedophile_Hunters_Accepted.pdf (Accessed: 17/10/2024)

Goffman, E. (1963). *Stigma: notes on the management of spoiled identity*. Harmondsworth: Penguin.

Gordon, K.E. (2013). The registered sex offender population as a marker of social disorganisation. *The Howard Journal of Criminal Justice*, 52(5), pp.527–542. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/hojo.12024> (Accessed: 15/11/2024)

- Gray, D.C., Cooper, M. and McAloon, D. (2012). The Supreme Court's Contemporary Silver Platter Doctrine. *Texas Law Review*, 91. [Online] Available at: <https://texaslawreview.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/08/Gray-Cooper-McAloon-91-TLR-7.pdf> (Accessed: 14/11/2024)
- Grossi, L. M. (2017). Sexual offenders, violent offenders, and community reentry: Challenges and treatment considerations. *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, 34, pp.59–67. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2017.04.005> (Accessed: 12/12/24)
- Hadjimatheou, K. (2019). Citizen-led digital policing and democratic norms: The case of self-styled paedophile hunters. *Criminology & Criminal Justice*, 21(4), pp.547–565. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1748895819880956> (Accessed on: 17/10/2024)
- Hadlington, L., Lumsden, K., Black, A. and Ferra, F. (2018). A Qualitative Exploration of Police Officers' Experiences, Challenges, and Perceptions of Cybercrime. *Policing: A Journal of Policy and Practice*, 15(1), pp.34–43. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/policing/pay090> (Accessed:13/01/2025)
- Hamilton, C. and Black, L. (2022). "Strikingly and Stubbornly High": Investigating the Paradox of Public Confidence in the Irish Police. *Journal of Contemporary Criminal Justice*, 39(1), pp.38-57. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/10439862221138672> (Accessed: 31/10/2024)
- Harkin, D. and Whelan, C. (2021). Perceptions of police training needs in cyber-crime. *International Journal of Police Science & Management*, 24(1), pp.66–76. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/14613557211036565> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)
- Harper, C. A., Hogue, T. E., and Bartels, R. M. (2017). Attitudes towards sexual offenders: What do we know, and why are they important? *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, 34, pp.201–213. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2017.01.011> (Accessed: 31/10/2024)
- Harper, C. A., Rumney, P. N. S. and Sackey, D. A. (2024). Are Sex Offending Allegations Viewed Differently? Exploring the Effect of Offense Type and Conviction Status on Criminal Stigmatization. *Sexual Abuse*, 36(1), pp.33-58. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/10790632231154168> (Accessed: 31/10/2024)
- Harris, A. J. and Socia, K. M. (2016). What's in a Name? Evaluating the Effects of the "Sex Offender" Label on Public Opinions and Beliefs. *Sexual Abuse*, 28(7), pp.660-678. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1079063214564391> (Accessed: 05/12/24)

Holmes, A.M. (2021). Citizen Led Policing in the Digital Realm: Paedophile Hunters and Article 8 in the case of Sutherland v Her Majesty's Advocate. *Modern Law Review*, 85(1), pp.219–231. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2230.12653>. (Accessed: 26/06/2025)

Holt, T. J., Bossler, A. M. and Seigfried-Spellar, K. C. (2017). Cybercrime and digital forensics. *Routledge eBooks*. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315296975> (Accessed: 13/01/2025)

Hudson, B. A. and Okhuysen, G. A. (2008). Not with a Ten-Foot Pole: Core Stigma, Stigma Transfer, and Improbable Persistence of Men's Bathhouses. *Organization Science*, 20(1), pp.134–153. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.1080.0368> (Accessed: 13/11/2024)

Hussey, E., Richards, K., and Scott, J. (2022). Paedophile Hunters and Performing Masculinities Online. *Deviant Behavior*, 43(11), pp.1313-1330. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01639625.2021.1978278> (Accessed: 17/10/2024)

Ireland, L. (2022). The acquisition of legitimacy for civilian policing: A case study of pedophile hunting groups. *Crime Law and Social Change*, 79(2), pp.195–216. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10611-022-10045-y> (Accessed: 17/10/2024)

Jahnke, S. (2018). Emotions and Cognitions Associated with the Stigma of Non-Offending Pedophilia: A Vignette Experiment. *Archives of Sexual Behavior*, 47(2), pp.363–373. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10508-017-1073-7> (Accessed: 31/10/2024)

Jahnke, S., Blagden, N. and Hill, L. (2022). Pedophile, Child Lover, or Minor-Attracted Person? Attitudes Toward Labels Among People Who are Sexually Attracted to Children. *Archives of Sexual Behavior*, 51(8), pp.4125–4139. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10508-022-02331-6>. (Accessed: 16/01/2025)

Jewkes, Y. and Wykes, M. (2012). Reconstructing the sexual abuse of children: 'cyber-paeds', panic and power. *Sexualities*, 15(8), pp. 934–952 [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1363460712459314> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Jewkes, Y. and Yar, M. (2010). *Handbook of Internet crime*. Cullompton: Willan. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781843929338> (Accessed: 26/02/2025)

Johnson, C., Dowd, T. J. and Ridgeway, C. L. (2006). Legitimacy as a Social Process. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 32, pp.53–78. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.soc.32.061604.123101> (Accessed: 13/11/2024)

Johnson, D., Faulkner, E., Meredith, G. and Wilson, T.J. (2020). Police Functional Adaptation to the Digital or Post Digital Age: Discussions with Cybercrime Experts. *The Journal of Criminal Law*. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022018320952559> (Accessed: 13/01/2025)

Key, R., Underwood, A., Farnham, F., Marzano, L., and Hawton, K. (2021). Suicidal behavior in individuals accused or convicted of child sex abuse or indecent image offenses: Systematic review of prevalence and risk factors. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 51(4), pp.715–728. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/sltb.12749> (Accessed: 10/01/2025)

Kohm, S. A. (2009). Naming, shaming and criminal justice: Mass-mediated humiliation as entertainment and punishment. *Crime Media Culture an International Journal*, 5(2), pp.188–205. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741659009335724> (Accessed: 10/01/2025)

Lehmann, R. J. B., Schmidt, A. F. and Jahnke, S. (2020). Stigmatization of Paraphilias and Psychological Conditions Linked to Sexual Offending, *The Journal of Sex Research*, 58(4), pp. 438–447. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224499.2020.1754748> (Accessed: 31/10/2024)

Levenson, J. S. (2011). Community protection from sexual violence: Intended and unintended outcomes of American policies. In Boer, D.P., Eher, R., Craig, L.A., Miner, M.H. and Pfäfflin, F. (eds). *International perspectives on the assessment and treatment of sexual offenders: Theory, practice, and research*, pp.587–607. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119990420.ch31> (Accessed: 15/11/2024)

Levenson, J. S. and Cotter, L. P. (2005). The effect of Megan’s law on sex Offender reintegration. *Journal of Contemporary Criminal Justice*, 21(1), pp.49–66. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1043986204271676> (Accessed: 15/11/2024)

Loveluck, B. (2019). The many shades of digital vigilantism. A typology of online self-justice. *Global Crime*, 21(3–4), pp.213–241. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17440572.2019.1614444> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Lubbe, W., Ham-Baloyi, W. and Smit, K. (2020). The integrative literature review as a research method: A demonstration review of research on neurodevelopmental supportive care in preterm infants. *Journal of Neonatal Nursing*, 26(6), pp.308–315. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnn.2020.04.006>. (Accessed: 26/02/2025)

Marsh, I. and Melville, G. (2011). Moral Panics and the British Media - A look at some contemporary folk devils. *Internet Journal of Criminology*. [Online] Available at:

https://www.academia.edu/2153760/Moral_Panics_and_the_British_Media_A_look_at_some_contemporray_Folk_Devils_ (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Mazerolle, L., Bennett, S., Davis, J., Sargeant, E. and Manning, M. (2013). Legitimacy in Policing: A Systematic Review. *Campbell Systematic Reviews*, 9(1). [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4073/csr.2013.1> (Accessed: 16/01/2025)

McAlinden, A. (2005). The Use of 'Shame' with Sexual Offenders. *The British Journal of Criminology*, 45(3), pp.373–394. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjc/azh095> (Accessed: 13/12/24)

McDonald, D. (2014). The politics of hate crime: neoliberal vigilance, vigilantism and the question of paedophilia. *International Journal for Crime, Justice and Social Democracy*, 3(1), pp.68–80. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5204/ijcjsd.v3i1.140> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

McPherson, R. (2020). Sutherland v HM Advocate: the right to privacy, evidence gathering and the integrity of justice in a digital age. *Juridical Review*, 2020(2), pp.104-109. [Online] Available at: <https://eprints.gla.ac.uk/223375/2/223375.pdf> (Accessed: 21/10/2024)

Moran, D. A. (2003). In defense of the corpus delicti rule. *Ohio State Law Journal*, 64, pp.817-854. [Online] Available at: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/159581293.pdf> (Accessed: 17/01/2025)

Morrell, K., Bradford, B., and Javid, B. (2019). What does it mean when we ask the public if they are 'confident' in policing? The trust, fairness, presence model of 'public confidence.' *International Journal of Police Science & Management*, 22(2), pp.111–122. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461355719891197> (Accessed: 13/11/2024)

Murphy, S. A. and Kiffin-Petersen, S. (2016). The exposed self: a multilevel model of shame and ethical behavior. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 141(4), pp.657–675. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-016-3185-8> (Accessed: 05/12/2024)

Noble, W. (2017). Cyber vigilantism – How the cyber mob behaves. In: *Owen, T., Noble, W., & Speed, F. C. eds. New Perspectives on Cybercrime*. Springer International Publishing, pp.45-61. [Online] Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-53856-3_4 (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Noppe, J., Verhage, A. and Van Damme, A. (2017). Police legitimacy: an introduction. *Policing: An International Journal*, 40(3), pp.474-479. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/PIJPSM-05-2017-0058> (Accessed: 13/01/2025)

- Norlock, K.J. (2017). Online Shaming. *Social Philosophy Today*, 33, pp.187-197. [Online] Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5840/socphiltoday201762343> (Accessed: 12/12/24)
- NPCC. (2017). *Police approach to paedophile hunters has not changed*. National Police Chiefs' Council (NPCC). [Online] Available at: <https://news.npcc.police.uk/releases/police-approach-to-paedophile-hunters-has-not-changed> (Accessed: 19/10/2024)
- NPCC. (2021). *Final National Public Order - Public Safety Strategic Risk Assessment ("POPS SRA") Spring 2021*. England: NPCC. [Online] Available at: https://www.npcc.police.uk/SysSiteAssets/media/downloads/publications/disclosure-logs/operations-coordination-committee/158-2022-final-pops-sra-spring-2021-v3-redacted_final.pdf (Accessed: 19/10/2024)
- Olver, M. E. and Barlow, A. A. (2010). Public attitudes toward sex offenders and their relationship to personality traits and demographic characteristics. *Behavioral sciences & the law*, 28(6), pp.832–849. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/bsl.959> (Accessed: 31/10/2024)
- Ost, S. (2009). *Child pornography and sexual grooming*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9780511730047> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)
- Phillips, S. D. and Gates, T. (2011). A conceptual framework for understanding the stigmatization of children of incarcerated parents. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 20(3), pp.286–294. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10826-010-9391-6> (Accessed: 05/12/24)
- Police Professional. (2017). *Forces 'may consider' working with so-called paedophile hunters*. Police Professional. [Online] Available at: <https://www.policeprofessional.com/news/forces-mayconsider-working-with-so-called-paedophile-hunters/> (Accessed: 19/10/2024).
- Purshouse, J. (2020). 'Paedophile hunters', criminal procedure, and fundamental human rights. *Journal of Law and Society*, 47(3), pp.384–411. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jols.12235> (Accessed: 17/10/2024)
- Randolph, J. J. (2009). A guide to writing the dissertation Literature Review. *Practical Assessment, Research & Evaluation*, 14(13), pp.1-12. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7275/b0az-8t74> (Accessed: 21/11/2024)
- Robbers, M. L. P. (2008). Lifers on the outside. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*, 53(1), pp.5–28. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306624x07312953> (Accessed: 13/12/24)

Rowe, J. (2015). *Paedophile hunter jailed for blackmail*. The Bury Times. [Online]. December 10th. Available at: https://www.burytimes.co.uk/news/14136397.Paedophile_hunter_jailed_for_blackmail/ (Accessed: 09/01/2025)

Schultz, C. (2014). The Stigmatization of Individuals Convicted of Sex Offenses: Labeling Theory and The Sex Offense Registry. *Themis: Research Journal of Justice Studies and Forensic Science*, 2(4). [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.31979/THEMIS.2014.0204> (Accessed: 12/12/24)

Sharp, D., Atherton, S. and Williams, K. (2008). Civilian policing, legitimacy and vigilantism: findings from three case studies in England and Wales. *Policing and Society*, 18(3), pp. 245–257. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10439460802091419> (Accessed: 13/11/2024)

Sieber, J. E. (1993). Ethical considerations in planning and conducting research on human subjects. *Academic Medicine*, 68(9), S9–S13. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1097/00001888-199309000-00028> (Accessed: 13/01/2025)

Silke, A. (2001). Dealing with Vigilantism: Issues and Lessons for the Police. *The Police Journal Theory Practice and Principles*, 74(2), pp.120–133. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0032258x0107400204> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Snyder, H. (2019). Literature review as a research methodology: An overview and guidelines. *Journal of Business Research*, 104, pp.333–339. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.07.039> (Accessed: 19/11/2024)

Sorell, T. (2019). Scambaiting on the spectrum of digilantism. *Criminal Justice Ethics*, 38(3), pp.153–175. [Online] <https://doi.org/10.1080/0731129x.2019.1681132> (Accessed: 17/10/2024)

Stark, F. (2018). *Non-state Entrapment*. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.34495> (Accessed: 21/10/2024)

Stratton, G., Powell, A. and Cameron, R. (2017). Crime and Justice in Digital Society: Towards a ‘Digital Criminology’?. *International Journal for Crime, Justice and Social Democracy*, 6(2), pp.17-33. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5204/ijcjsd.v6i2.355> (Accessed: 17/10/2024)

Suchman, M. C. (1995). Managing legitimacy: Strategic and institutional approaches. *The Academy of Management Review*, 20(3), pp.571–610. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/258788> (Accessed: 13/11/2024)

Suddaby, R., Bitektine, A., and Haack, P. (2017). Legitimacy. *Academy of Management Annals*, 11(1), pp.451–478. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5465/annals.2015.0101> (Accessed: 13/11/2024)

Suri, H. (2020). Ethical considerations of conducting systematic reviews in educational research. In: *Zawacki-Richter, O., Kerres, M., Bedenlier, S., Bond, M., & Buntins, K. (eds). Systematic reviews in educational research: Methodology, perspectives and application*, pp.41-54. [Online] Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-27602-7_3 (Accessed: 21/11/2024)

Thomas, B., Tachble, A., Peiris, D., Malhi, R., Godlovitch, G. and Lin, Y. (2015). Making Literature Reviews More Ethical: a Researcher and Health Sciences Librarian Collaborative Process. *Future Science OA*, 1(4). [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4155/fso.15.78> (Accessed: 21/11/2024)

Thomason, K. K. (2021). The moral risks of online shaming. In: *Véliz, C. (ed). Oxford Handbook of Digital Ethics*, pp. 145–162. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198857815.013.8> (Accessed: 13/12/24)

Tippett, A. (2022) The rise of paedophile hunters: To what extent are cyber-vigilante groups a productive form of policing, retribution and justice?. *Criminology & Criminal Justice*. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/17488958221136845> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Torraco, R. J. (2005). Writing Integrative Literature Reviews: Guidelines and Examples. *Human Resource Development Review*, 4(3), pp.356–367. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484305278283> (Accessed: 19/11/2024)

Trottier, D. (2017). Digital Vigilantism as Weaponisation of Visibility. *Philosophy & technology*, 30(1), pp.55–72. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-016-0216-4>. (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Trottier, D. (2019). Denunciation and doxing: towards a conceptual model of digital vigilantism. *Global Crime*, 21(3–4), pp.196–212. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17440572.2019.1591952> (Accessed: 21/11/2024)

Tyler, T.R. and Fagan, J. (2008). *Legitimacy and Cooperation: Why Do People Help the Police Fight Crime in Their Communities?*. *Ohio State Journal of Criminal Law*, 6, pp.231–275. [Online] Available at: https://scholarship.law.columbia.edu/faculty_scholarship/414/ (Accessed: 16/01/2025)

Walton, K. and Penfold, R. (2023). Paedophile hunters and the road to injustice. In: Johnston, E. ed. *Challenges in Criminal Justice*. Oxon: Routledge, pp.164-179. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003143321-10> (Accessed: 17/10/2024)

Weber, M. (1968). *Economy and society: An outline of interpretive sociology*. New York: Bedminster Press.

Welsh, L., Skinns, L. and Sanders, A. (2021). *Sanders & Young's Criminal Justice*. Oxford University Press. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/he/9780199675142.001.0001>. (Accessed: 03/03/2025)

Wodda, A. (2018). Stranger Danger!. *Journal of Family Strengths*, 18(1). [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.58464/2168-670X.1384> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Wolf, M.R. and Pruitt, D.K. (2019). Grooming Hurts Too: The Effects of Types of Perpetrator Grooming on Trauma Symptoms in Adult Survivors of Child Sexual Abuse. *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse*, 28(3), pp.345–359. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10538712.2019.1579292> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)

Yardley, E., Lynes, A. G. T., Wilson, D. and Kelly, E. (2016). What's the deal with 'websleuthing'? News media representations of amateur detectives in networked spaces. *Crime Media Culture an International Journal*, 14(1), pp.81–109. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741659016674045> (Accessed: 18/10/2024)